

CONJUNCTION "WITH" IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS ISSUE

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As in other Turkic languages, the word "bilan (with)" is used mainly as an auxiliary in Uzbek. But in the Uzbek language, it also has a connecting function. This was first mentioned by Sh.Sh. Shoabdurahmanov. He includes the word with as a conjunction in the series of conjunctions. It is also shown that its connector connects two organized parts to each other and conveys the information of unity, one following the other. After that, his opinion was repeated in a number of literature. For example, this is observed in the first volume of "Current Uzbek Literary Language" published in 1966 under the seal of the Academy¹, and in the "Textbook of Uzbek Language"² published by M. Mirzayev, S. Usmonov, and I. Rasulov for the faculties of pedagogy. Even the supporting part was written by Sh. Shoabdurahmanov and published under

ABSTRACT

In this article, the cases of the conjunction with in the Uzbek language, as well as in Turkic languages, are analyzed as both auxiliary and connecting.

the stamp of the Academy. The same idea is repeated in the first book of "Uzbek Language Grammar"³ and in the first book of "Current Uzbek Literary Language"⁴ intended for philology faculties of pedagogical institutes. Only N.N. Koklyanova added a new idea to it in her article. In this case, it is indicated that if it is connected with the associated possessor by means of a conjunction, its participle is used in the plural.

A more detailed idea about all the functional characteristics of a liaison officer is given only in T. Rustamov's book dedicated to assistants.⁵ Therefore, we considered it necessary to check the materials we collected from our own point of view and compare them with the points of view of T. Rustamov.

¹ Modern Uzbek literary language. Book 1 / edited by G'.A. Abdurahmanov. - T.: Fan, 1966. - B.361.

² Mirzayev M., Usmanov S., Rasulov I. Uzbek language. -T.: Teacher, 1970. -B.162

³ Grammar of the Uzbek language. Book 1.-T.: Fan, 1975. -B.569.

⁴ Modern Uzbek literary language. Part 1.-T.: Oqituvhchi, 1980. -B.406.

⁵ Rustamov T. Helpers in modern Uzbek literary language. -T.: Science, 1965. -P.36-59

As noted by T. Rustamov, the assistant is used not only as an assistant, but also as a connector⁶. But his progress in this task did not take place in the conditions that came naturally to him. Its certain informatic connotation has developed and created a connecting function. In this case, it can be assumed that it has the following auxiliary function: the subordinate component of the compound governed by the verb formed by means of it shows the person who participated in the performance of the action. Its grammatical meaning is also noted in the monographs of F.Abdullayev and F.Ibrohimova.⁷ As an example of this, Qabilbabo cites the example of the council with his friends (A. Qahhor). As can be seen from the example, both Grandfather who performed the action and his companions who participated in the management are individuals. Therefore, one of them does not become a tool in the act of action for the other. The part of the sentence formed on top of that is also a verb in the unity ratio. This act of action makes the agent and the counterparty equal in performance of the action. From a grammatical point of view, the word Kabilbabo, which is the owner of the sentence, and the complementing word "Yor-friends" give equal expression in the performance of the action as an organized part. That is why such sentences can be easily transformed into an organized possessive sentence without any change in terms of form. We said about it above. That is: Kabilbabo consulted with his friends. The following examples also have this character: Zufarjon dug a well with Dangal's sons for three

days (Sh. Ashurova). The news that Namaz was walking around the market place with the prayer boys spread everywhere in an instant (K. Tokhtaboyev). She ran away with a guy when her sister was graduating from the tenth grade (Kh. Sultonov).

It is also possible to do the opposite of such a transformation, i.e., the first possessor is taken before the second, and the first possessor is turned into a complement. For example, Shorlik's shoemaker and his old woman kept crying (O. Husanov). Let's change the first form of the possessive in this sentence into a complement by means of transformation: His old lady is crying hard with a salty shoe. The semantics of this transformed sentence does not differ at all from the semantics of the previous sentence. That is why he shows that if there is a pause after the auxiliary of possessive clauses, which has been combined with D. Ashurova,⁸ it becomes a filler. However, T. Rustamov criticizes it and says that the semantics of unity in them is preserved.⁹ That's right. However, if we take into account that the auxiliary also forms the counterpart as a complement in the control of the verb, we can see that it is characteristic of the auxiliary with the semantics of unity. This fact shows that T. Rustamov's objection is incorrect.

The auxiliary with has the same functional properties as the conjunctions (and, as well as) in the same position. However, it differs from them in its own aspects.

1. Connecting connectors can perform their function in the union of two or more parts. For example, a white, red and yellow

⁶ Rustamov T. That book. - B. 56-59.

⁷ Abdullayev L.F., Ibrahimova F. Management in Uzbek language.-T.: Fan, 1982. -B.105.

⁸ Ashurova D. On the use of conjunctions in united clauses//Uzbek language and literature. -Tashkent, 1960. -#2.-B.52.

⁹ Rustamov T. Helpers in modern Uzbek literary language. . -T.: Science, 1965. -B.58.

flower opened. There will be no more than two owners organized by means of a joint venture.

2. If the possessor and the conjunctive conjunction perform exactly the same action, this performance may be unrelated to each other. It shows that they performed the same action together with the possessive participle. For example, brother Melivoi and Bekmurod stared at a new companion (O. Husanov). In this sentence, the action understood from the verb to stare was performed jointly by the persons understood from the words Melivoi aka and Bekmurod. Their observation is not disconnected from each other. That is why the plural given in the verb is a stylistic necessity. If we use the conjunction and in the place of the auxiliary in the sentence, a certain semantic change will occur in the semantics of the sentence. In this case, although it is expressed that the persons understood from Melivoy brother, Bekmurod performed the action understood from the verb to stare, it is expressed that this action was performed independently without dependence on each other. Therefore, the verb does not require a plural form in this case. Note: Brother Melivoi and Bekmurod stared at the new companion.

3. One of the possessors united by means of bilan can be transferred to the complement by means of transformation. For example, the Kazakh Russians colluded with the "Shurai Islamists" and wanted to take Jizzakh first, then switch to Kokan (O. Husanov). In this sentence, the agent of the sentence is both the association of "Shurai Islamists" and the association of Kazakh Russians. Their association was shaped by their liaison and assistant. The first agent

can be transformed into a complement by means of its helper, that is, the sentence can be transformed. Please note: Kazakh Russians colluded with "Shurai Islamists" and wanted to take Jizzakh first, then move to Kokan. In this sentence, the association of "shurai Islamists" was not an agent of the organized owner, but a counterparty. One of the organized possessives cannot be turned into a complement by means of conjunctive conjunctions. That is, one of the two agents with a connecting link cannot be transferred to the counterpart through sentence transformation. For example, Botirali and Nizomiddinov remained in the Directorate (S. Ahmad). The agents of this sentence are manifested in the words Botirali, Nizomiddinov, and their first component cannot be transferred to the function of a complement along with a connector, that is, it cannot be manifested as a counterpart. Please note: Nizomiddinov Botirali remained in the office.

It seems that the speech is not stylistically formed. Therefore, the possessive clauses with a conjunctive conjunction do not have the possibility of transformation.

4. If one of the joint owners formed by means of Bilan is the first or second person, it is also possible to support them implicitly. In this case, without reaching the semantics of the sentence, it moves to the function of possessive complement. For example, he and I never talked about you (E. Usmanov). Why weren't you with Pardaboy? (O. Husanov). In these sentences, if we put first or second person singular pronouns after the helper with, then the organized possessor is restored. There will be no change in the semantics of the sentence. Such a transformation is not possible in conjunctive conjunctions. That

is, you and Mabodo Pardaboy weren't together? cannot be changed to

5. Conjunctions can connect all denotative words and act as a means for them to come together. But has a limited role as a conjunction. It only serves as a tool for combining nouns and pronouns.

6. All pieces organized by means of connecting links can come in the same form. When the conjunction with but is used as a conjunction, only the following clause can appear in some form. For example, except for Bukhara and Khiva, everywhere looked towards the republic (O. Husanov). In this sentence, it is connected with the words Bukhara and Khiva through its helper. Only the last of them came with the form of the suffix. It is not possible for both parts of this form to occur. This would be possible if the auxiliary word with were in place and the auxiliary word was used. Note: except for Bukhara and Khiva, everywhere has turned towards the republic.

These features of the auxiliary word in the function of a connecting link arise from its auxiliary function and are related to the semantics of the formation of the complement representing the counterparty, which we noted above.

It is a very common phenomenon that the auxiliary bilan is formed as a connector. That is why, as mentioned in the article of A.A. Koklyanova, the monograph of

F.Abdullayev, F.Ibrohimova, the participle in the recorded sentence is plural. For example, Yolchi Ibrahimov and Ahmadjon Klebnev spoke again that day (O. Husanov). In Alamzada, Mirza Hakim and Zamonbek's servants rode around the village of Shahob (Kh. Tokhtaboyev).

As a conjunction, it also performs its function in connecting other parts of the sentence.

1. It acts as a link in the association of determiners. For example, Namozboy was very sorry for the situation of Ammo Hayitboy and Tokhtashvoy (K. Tokhtaboyev).

2. When the case of place is combined. For example, there are many places of pilgrimage in Samarkand and Bukhara.

3. The filler acts as a binder when combined. For example, Sattorjon took the prayer with a pen.

The word bilan is used as an auxiliary as well as a conjunction. The occurrence of the auxiliary word bilan in the function of conjunction was caused by the development of its formation in the function of complement. According to the function of the connecting link with, it is among the conjunctive connectives. However, it differs from it in that it is functionally limited, prone to transformation, and cannot organize more than two parts. He can connect different parts of the sentence.

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